

Digital
Citizenship

Media and Information Literacy Course

Readings | Exercises | Case studies | Quizzes

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Strategic partnership to develop open educational resources for teaching digital citizenship

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Abstract	<p>The importance of being a media and information literate person is crucial nowadays because we are living in the 21st century, which challenges us with the rapid growth of technologies.</p> <p>Information is everywhere and it is our job to select and use the proper one. This course is intended to provide tips and tricks to develop your digital citizenship skills. It comprises 5 modules, case studies and practical tasks that will help you develop a combined set of competencies (knowledge, skills and attitude) necessary for your entire life.</p> <p>Those competencies will give you advantages in our modern world today especially in terms of using the freedom of expression, gathering information, evaluating false and accurate information as well as in producing information where needed.</p>
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Introduction

Media and Information Literacy (MIL) enables people to *interpret and make informed judgments* as users of information and media, as well as to become skillful *creators and producers* of information and media messages.

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines MIL as the:

"Set of competencies to search, critically evaluate, use and contribute information and media content wisely; knowledge of one's rights online; understanding how to combat online hate speech and cyberbullying; understanding of the ethical issues surrounding the access and use of information; and engage with media and ICTs to promote equality, free expression, intercultural/interreligious dialogue, peace, etc." (UNESCO, 2016).

MIL combines media literacy and information literacy under one concept, and includes a combination of competencies (knowledge, skills and attitude) necessary for life and work today.

Media literacy emphasizes the ability to:

- understand media functions
- evaluate how they are performed
- use them for self-expression

Information literacy emphasizes:

- the importance of access to information
- the evaluation of information
- ethical use of such information.

For sure, all of us recognize the primary role of information and media in our everyday lives. MIL focuses on the freedom of expression and information since it empowers citizens to understand the functions of media and other information providers, to evaluate their content, and to make informed criticism as users and producers of information and media content.

Why is this course needed? As David Berlo mentioned in his book "Communication and Behavior" (Hanneman, McEwen, & Berlo, 1975):

"Most of what we have called formal education has been intended to imprint on the human mind all of the information that we might need for a lifetime. Education is geared toward information storage. Today that is neither possible nor necessary. Rather, humankind needs to be taught how to process information that is stored through [new and old media] technology. Education needs to be geared toward the handling of [information and knowledge] data rather than the accumulation of data."

His words are actual than ever. With the explosion of information that we face every day, it becomes irrelevant to ask students to learn about facts and to evaluate their achievements by answering questions on tests. The key is rethinking education.

1. Module 1 - Why media literacy skills

Upon completing this module, you will be able to:

- Understand media content and its uses
- Explain the role and functions of media in democratic societies
- Describe how communication is affected by media and information

Media and information literacy

The word "literacy" usually describes the ability to read and write.

Media Literacy – the ability to access, analyze, evaluate, and create media in a variety of forms. With the constant change and evolution of media, the definition was expanded and it “refers to analytical/reflective understanding of printed and electronic mass media, including film, their aesthetic components, institutional structures, socioeconomic contexts, and an ability to interact with media in preparing audiovisual products and in influencing media decision-makers” (Brown, 2001).

The aim of the module “Media literacy” is to empower individuals and provide them with the ability to become critical consumers and creators of media.

Information Literacy – the ability to recognize when information is needed and locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information.

The aim of the module “Information literacy” is to enable people to interpret and make informed judgments as users of information sources, as well as to become producers of information in their own right.

What is media

Media are powerful forces in the lives of youth. Music, TV, video games, magazines and other media all have a strong influence on how we see the world, an influence that often begins in infancy. Actually, any form of communication that carries a message is a medium. This can include things we might be aware of, like magazines, television, radio and the Internet; and also less obvious things, like text messages and branded logos on clothes.

Dictionary: plural of medium = media

“The media” – means channels of communication between a person or persons and their intended audience

To be engaged and critical media consumers, we need to develop skills and habits of media literacy. These skills include:

- to be able to access media on a basic level,
- to analyse it critically based on certain key concepts,
- to evaluate it based on that analysis and, finally,
- to produce media oneself.

This process of learning media literacy skills is media education.

Role of media

The purpose of media is to give information about current news, gossips, fashion, culture, public relations and the latest gadgets in the marketplace to the people. Some of the roles of media in society are:

- Communication
- Create events
- Entertainment
- Advertisement
- Socialization
- Brand awareness

Nowadays, media is an integral part of our life and it influences society in many ways. It has the power to mobilize mass movement, helps people to get information about a lot of things, form opinions and make a judgment regarding various issues. It is the media, which keeps people updated and informed about what is happening around them and the world that everyone draws something from it.

Example 1. Think about the first printing machine

The invention of printing from movable type in the 15th century and the Protestant Reformation in the 16th further increased the numbers of people able to hold and express informed opinions on contemporary issues. The German priest and scholar Martin Luther broke with the humanists by abandoning the use of Classical Latin, which was intelligible only to the educated, and turned directly to the masses. “I will gladly leave to others the honour of doing great things,” he wrote, “and will not be ashamed of preaching and writing in German for the unschooled layman.” (Davison, 2020)

Self-reflection challenge: What was the role of media?

Example 2. Think about sensory marketing

Every time we bite a MAGNUM ice cream bar and we hear that “cracking” sound, whenever we walk into a ZARA store and we smell that singular “spicy” scent – we are interacting with the brand way beyond sliding our credit cards. Senses trigger strong emotions and memories in us. Brands know this and they exploit it to their advantage. (Harald, 2020)

Self-reflection challenge: Think about another example.

Source: (Harald, 2020)

Example 3. Think about the spread of information

In a research study, experts from MIT Media Lab simulated how people could use social media (such as Facebook and Twitter) to find 10 weather balloons, hidden randomly throughout the continental United States, over the course of several hours. They demonstrated it was possible to find the balloons using social media alone, without any help from traditional mass media, like TV or radio broadcasts. The findings show that highly connected people with broad geographic social networks are essential to the successful mobilization of society (Hardesty, 2009).

Actually, the U.S. Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) launched a competition: 10 large red weather balloons would be raised at undisclosed locations across the United States; the first team to use social media — like online social networks and communication systems — to determine the correct latitude and longitude of all 10 would receive \$40,000.

Result: On Saturday morning the balloons went up, and by the end of the day the MIT team had won the competition.

Source: (Hardesty, 2009)

The approach: The MIT team's approach was an incentive structure — a way of splitting up the prize money among people who helped find a balloon. Whoever provided the balloon's correct coordinates

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got \$2,000; but whoever invited that person to join the network got \$1,000; whoever invited that person got \$500; and so on. No matter how long the chain got, the total payment would never quite reach \$40,000; whatever was left over went to charity.

The MIT team pointed out that they used “broadcast” media to draw attention to its incentive scheme — posts on highly trafficked websites like slashdot.org. The news then diffused through a variety of social media, but claiming a share of the prize money required registering on the MIT team’s website, which is a “concentrating mechanism.” This is one example of combining different types of media.

Self-reflection challenge: What did the MIT team achieve?

Example 4. Think about a common cause

This is not about agreeing or not. It is about the power to mobilize masses of people.

The Human Rights Campaign is an NGO acting for human rights. They developed an iconic logo in 1995. As the Washington D.C. Supreme Court took up two cases of marriage equality in 2013, the HRC choose to change their Facebook profile picture to a red version of its logo in solidarity and asked others to follow suit. According to Facebook, 3 million people shared the logo, 800 variations were made, and the social network saw a 120% increase in profile photo updates (Canva, 2020).

This is just one example of how social media mobilizes people around the world for a common cause. The campaign went viral, and celebrities such as George Takei, Beyonce, Martha Stewart and others helped draw attention to the movement. (HRC, 2020).

Self-reflection challenge: Think about another example.

The role of media in a democratic society

The role of media in a democratic society (Shea, 1998) is to inform the public on what is going on:

- inform democratic choices through the clarification of complex issues;
- provoke public debates leading to greater public participation in important decisions;
- uncover abuses, pressure for their rectification;
- alert and mobilize public opinion to humanitarian causes/injustices;
- allow political pluralism to express itself by advertising different views/ ideological approaches to certain issues;
- keep politicians attuned to public opinion while offering politicians a medium to explain policies/decisions to public opinion and build the necessary support.

We shall know that impartial media is neither possible nor desirable. Most newspapers have political or ideological preferences and it is essential to maintain a distinction between facts and opinion, reporting and analysis. This is the point where our media literacy skills make a difference.

Certainly, the media affects people's perspectives. Too much intervention of media in everything is a matter of concern. Media can be considered as a "watchdog" of political democracy.

Source: Whoever controls the media, controls the mind. (Quotes, n.d.)

The quote talks about how reporters, the government, and anyone else who has control over the media, is "controlling" our minds by influencing our thoughts and opinions on certain topics. Those media reporters often put negative or positive "filters" on different issues to brainwash you to think in a certain way or style.

Why media literacy skills

Media literacy is the ability to identify different types of media and understand the messages they're sending. Young people take in a huge amount of information from a wide array of sources, far beyond the traditional media (TV, radio, newspapers, and magazines) of most adults. There are text messages, memes, viral videos, social media, video games, advertising, and more.

Focus: All media share one thing:

- Someone created it.
- It was created for a reason.
- Understanding that reason is the basis of media literacy.

The digital age has made it easy for anyone to create media. We don't always know who created something, why they made it, and whether it's credible. This makes media literacy tricky to learn and teach. Nonetheless, media literacy is an essential skill in the digital age. Specifically, it helps us:

Learn to think critically. As youth evaluate media, they decide whether the messages make sense, why certain information was included, what wasn't included, and what the key ideas are. They learn to use examples to support their opinions. Then they can make up their own minds about the information based on the knowledge they already have.

Become a smart consumer of products and information. Media literacy helps youth learn how to determine whether something is credible. It also helps them determine the "persuasive intent" of advertising and resist the techniques marketers use to sell products.

Recognize points of view. Every creator has a perspective. Identifying an author's point of view helps youth appreciate different perspectives. It also helps put information in the context of what they already know -- or think they know.

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Create media responsibly. Recognizing your own point of view, saying what you want to say how you want to say it, and understanding that your messages have an impact is key to effective communication.

Identify the role of media in our culture. From celebrity gossip to magazine covers to memes, media is telling us something, shaping our understanding of the world, and even compelling us to act or think in certain ways.

Understand the author's goal. What does the author want you to take away from a piece of media? Is it purely informative, is it trying to change your mind, or is it introducing you to new ideas you've never heard of? When youth understand what type of influence something has, they can make informed choices.

Professional support

Media literacy includes asking specific questions and backing up your opinions with examples. Following media-literacy steps allows you to learn for yourself what a given piece of media is, why it was made, and what you want to think about it. Experts recommend key questions to ask for developing media literacy skills (CommonSense, 2020):

- **AUTHOR** Who created this? Was it a company? Was it an individual? (If so, who?) Was it a comedian? Was it an artist? Was it an anonymous source? Why do you think that?
- **REASON** Why did they make it? Was it to inform you of something that happened in the world (for example, a news story)? Was it to change your mind or behaviour (an opinion essay or a how-to)? Was it to make you laugh (a funny meme)? Was it to get you to buy something (an ad)? Why do you think that?
- **AUDIENCE** Who is the message for? Is it for kids? Grown-ups? Girls? Boys? People who share a particular interest? Why do you think that?
- **AUTHORITY** What techniques are being used to make this message credible or believable? Does it have statistics from a reputable source? Does it contain quotes from a subject expert? Does it have an authoritative-sounding voice-over? Is there direct evidence of the assertions it is making? Why do you think that?
- **BALANCE** What details were left out, and why? Is the information balanced with different views -- or does it present only one side? Do you need more information to fully understand the message? Why do you think that?
- **FEELINGS** How did the message make you feel? Do you think others might feel the same way? Would everyone feel the same, or would certain people disagree with you? Why do you think that?

As you become more aware of and exposed to news and current events, you can apply media-literacy steps to radio, TV, and online information.

Key Concept: Your media literacy skills act as a filter. The media that you will see, hear, read or feel will go through your mindset filter to critically respond.

Exercise 1: Media audit

Objectives:

- Identify media around yourself
- Understand the impact of the huge amount of media and information
- Formulate feedback to your colleagues

Duration: 15 minutes

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Tools: pen, piece of paper / forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison

Description of the exercise: During this exercise, you will identify media and information that daily surround you. Then, you will compare it with a detailed list of media and you notice that some things might be omitted.

Tasks:

- Imagine that you are at the end of a typical school day.
- Now, take 10 minutes to make a list of all the media that you saw, heard, played or otherwise consumed today.
- Present it to your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all media discovered by your classmates.
- Compare your list with the consolidated list

Debriefing: Check your list again. Did you include some of the items below:

- Outdoor advertising (billboards, bus shelter ads, etc.)
- Product packaging in stores or in products they use at home (cereal boxes, for example)
- Logos or messages on clothing (yours and others')
- Posters, signs, pop and snack machines in school
- Text messages
- Background music in stores

Lessons learned: various information and media are around us and we are media consumers

Recommendations: Do not ignore messages. Even if you ignore them, it may happen those messages act at "unconscious level mind" and your decisions to be influenced by them.

Forum

Objectives:

- Identify media around you
- Structure the content and ideas
- Give feedback

You are invited to describe/ write down what you already know about the topic "Media" in the forum Know-Want-Learned.

Tasks:

- Share your media habits, lifestyles and preferences with your classmates
- Reply twice to your colleagues

Supplementary reading

Common Sense. (2020). <https://www.common sense media.org/news-and-media-literacy/what-is-media-literacy-and-why-is-it-important>

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2. Module 2 - Ask the right question

Upon completing this module, you will be able to:

- Identify sources of information
- Define information needs
- Determine the accuracy of the content

Information literacy

Nowadays, lots of information and many sources of information are available. Many of them are easily accessible on the internet. Sometimes we found ourselves with too much information. At this point, it is everyone's analytical and critical thinking abilities to determine whether the information will answer our question. Certainly, we all agree until this point. But what is our question? We need to define the question to ask.

Questions that need information occur daily: those for study purposes as well as for decisions in everyday life. You make decisions - therefore you need information to make good decisions. E.g.:

- School assignment (type of research, type of presentation)
- Make personal decisions (buy a mobile phone, a car or a house)
- Open a money-saving account

An information literate person recognizes when he/she needs information (UFH, 2020)

Information needs

Information need is an individual or group's desire to locate and obtain information to satisfy a conscious or unconscious need (Thanuskodi, 2015). The 'information' and 'needs' in 'information needs' are an inseparable interconnection. Needs and interests call forth information.

When we talk about needs, we recall the old, very actual and well-known pyramid of needs (Maslow, 1943). You may wonder where the information need is here in the pyramid. The answer is simple. Everywhere! It became more and more stringent as you go up in the pyramid.

While we became more conscientious about our needs, we will be able to formulate the right questions to ask, as well as to get proper responses.

Professional support

To better identify the information needs, librarians recommend a few guiding questions (LibGuides, 2020):

- What information do you need? Define your problem or interpret your assignment.
- What information do you already have on the subject? What facts or background information do you already know?
- Do you want general or specific information about the subject?
- How much information do you want? A single fact? A paragraph? A few pages? An entire book?
- What types of information do you want? For example, are you looking for:
 - opinions
 - statistics or data
 - case studies or specific examples
 - name of experts
 - historical information
 - analysis
- What information sources (databases, library catalogues, encyclopaedias, the Internet) will help you to find the information you need?

You might think that all those questions are for researchers, scientists and not for our daily routine queries. At some point, we would agree on that. “Information needs” was a term used in information science. Not so long time ago, the information need was related to the term relevance (Hjørland, 1997). According to this concept, if something is relevant for us in relation to a task (and we have many daily tasks), then we might say that we need information for that task. This is why information need is important at all levels.

Having the question defined will help us to easily understand the information needed. Please note that at the beginning, your question will not be perfect. Don't worry! Just ask the question, look for

information and find answers for that question. While you practice and search for answers, you will improve your questioning technique. For sure, other questions will raise. Actually, there is an art “The art of questioning”.

Until now, we have a topic and we identified that we need information about that topic. Defining the information needs includes a 5 steps process (UFH, 2020). Before starting to search and research on a certain topic, be sure that you formulated the draft question in your mind. Knowing what you are looking for, will help you recognize that you have found your answer. Then, let’s take a look!

Case study - Buy a telephone

This case study is a 5 steps adaptation (UFH, 2020):

Step 1 – Start. Decision

You have decided to buy a mobile phone, so you realize that you need information to be able to make an informed decision. It is important to think about your need and write down everything you know or need to know, e.g.

- What type of mobile phone do you want to buy?
- What is the size of your budget?
- Which colour do you want?
- Which model do you need/want?
- Should the mobile phone have certain features?

Step 2 – Find information. Search

You have recognized your need and must find the necessary information to help you in making the correct decision. The following are possible sources of information:

- Read the magazine or newspaper to see what is being advertised.
- Look for the latest news, prices and comparisons of different models on the market
- Search the Internet (websites specialized for mobile phones).
- Discusses with a person, friend, professional who has the necessary technical knowledge about mobile phones.
- Search the internet for information on mobile phone suppliers

Step 3 – Evaluate the information. Evaluate

Always check the authenticity of the information you receive, especially information received from another person (secondhand information). People, reviewers, sells persons can provide the wrong information.

You must make sure before you base an important decision on information received. For example:

- When discussing with somebody who can give you technical advice on buying a mobile phone, make sure that you can trust his / her advice by considering:
 - The person's background and formal experience in this field.
 - Is the person trustworthy?
- When checking reviews on the internet, consider the following:
 - Is there sufficient quantitative and qualitative information?
 - The review can be fake

Step 4 – Use the information. Use/Apply

Plagiarism and copyright are serious offences. Plagiarism is intellectual theft. Any use of another author's research, ideas, or language without proper attribution may be considered plagiarism (Gordon, Simmons, & Wynn, 2002). Use the information responsibly:

- Collecting information and using it for your own to buy a mobile phone does not mean that you break the law. You just base your decision on the information that you gathered.

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- Illegal use: If you present that same information as your own ideas in blog articles, documents, papers, etc. under your name.

Step 5 - Communicate the information. Communicate

Communicating information is what you do when you write a report, do a presentation or designing a poster, etc. Communicate your information to other people.

- When you buy a mobile phone, you will verbally convey the information to the salesperson.

Exercise 2: Define information needs

Objectives:

- Define information needs
- Collect, evaluate and compare potential sources of media and information
- Use the information and communicate

Duration: 30 minutes

Tools: internet, colleagues, phone

Methods: search, discussion with peers

Description of the exercise: During this exercise, trainees are required to prepare themselves for a situation that may occur in their daily life. Imagine that your father gets a new job and you are going to move together with your family to a new city, to a new school with new colleagues. You are going to start a new semester there. How do you prepare for this?

Tasks:

- Explore the new concept of defining information needs
- Review the case study
- Collect materials/ videos/ photos or articles
- Make observations
- Communicate
- Challenge: Present the answers to the 5 Key questions to your classmates

Debriefing: At the end of presentations, evaluate once again your answers.

- Did you miss information that you wanted to have on your list?
- What makes a particular source of information or media platform appealing and useful?
- How did you evaluate the gathered information?
- Why do young people prefer to use the internet rather than traditional media?

Lessons learned: the question is the key to being sure that your research will go in the right direction.

Recommendations: No matter how much or little information you found, bear in mind: how found information is related to your scope.

Forum

Objectives:

- Identify the right information for your task
- Structure the content and ideas
- Give feedback

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You are going to open a money-saving account. Share with your colleagues the main sources of information that you are going to use.

Tasks:

- Share the necessary sources of information to open a bank account
- Reply twice to your colleagues

Supplementary reading

University of Fort Hare. (2020). Information literacy - A student's resource to learn information skills for success. <https://www.ufh.ac.za/library/InfoLit/index.html>

3. Module 3 - Legal, ethical and societal aspects of using media and information

Upon completing this module, you will be able to:

- Access information effectively and efficiently
- Understand the key concept that media have social and political implications
- Understand the idea that media products may have both explicit and implicit messages
- Identify implicit messages in a media text
- Put into practice the understanding of the intellectual property

Legal aspects

Very often, when we think about the legal use of media and information, intellectual property and copyright come into our minds. Intellectual property (IP) refers to creations of the mind, such as inventions, literary and artistic works, designs, and symbols, names and images used in commerce.

The origins of intellectual property law can be traced thousands of years ago, as a response to the rise of commerce. Later, with the development of technologies for the reproduction and distribution of works the need for harmonization and protection of authorship occur. Internet and digitalization brought new challenges and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) attempted to standardize the regulation of copyright and neighbouring rights in the digital environment (De Filippi, 2012).

Let's see a few examples of properties covered and protected by intellectual property law.

(Ping, 2017)

Copyright

A copyright protects an original artistic or literary work. E.g. books, music, movies, pictures, graphics, and sculptures. The notice should look like this: © [year] by [name of owner]

Copyright sign. Source: (www.cleanpng.com)

France is the first country to have implemented an authors' right regime, first with the enactment of the Law of 1791, which introduced the exclusive right of representation, then with the Law of 1793, recognizing the exclusive right of reproduction to authors (De Filippi, 2012).

Patent

A patent protects an invention. E.g. ornamental designs of jewelry, furniture, beverage containers, computer icons

US design patent D48,160 for the original Coca-Cola bottle. (Manske, 2008)

The Venetian Senate enacted the first patent statute in 1474, providing the maker of any “new and ingenious device [...] reduced to perfection so that it can be used and operated” an exclusive license of 10 years to practice the invention (Menell, 2001).

Trademarks

A trademark typically protects brand names and logos used on goods and services. Although, a logo can be both protected by copyright and trademark (Asmus, 2018). Typically, a trademark covers a limited scope of situations; whereas copyright covers nearly all instances of copying that is affecting the original creator’s business and intent. Therefore, it’s not uncommon for larger corporations to protect their identity under both trademark and copyright.

Logo, Source: (Asmus, 2018)

The first use of trademarks can be traced back almost 4000 years to the earliest merchant societies in China, India, Persia, Egypt, Greece, and Rome where craftspeople marked their wares with distinctive symbols to identify the source of their goods, develop a distinctive reputation for quality, and assist in resolving ownership disputes (Menell, 2001).

Industrial design

An industrial design constitutes the ornamental aspect of an article.

Ingelec's single switch and socket design, internationally registered under the Hague system (Registration No. DM/065983) (WIPO, 2010)

The design of a product is often the main reason that consumers chose it over others. Industrial design rights protect the appearance of a product, which results from attributes such as its shape, colors or materials. The EU has harmonized industrial design protection across EU countries and introduced the Community design that offers unitary protection across the EU through a single procedure (EC, European Commission, 2020).

Geographical indication

The geographical indication includes the name of the place of origin of the goods.

Roquefort cheese protected under the EU Geographical Indication scheme (Astley, 2013)

Geographical indications and appellations of origin are signs used on goods that have a specific geographical origin and possess qualities, a reputation or characteristics that are essentially attributable to that place of origin (WIPO, 2010).

Trade secrets

Are rights on confidential information which may be sold or licensed.

“Any information that is secret (not generally known among or readily accessible to persons within the relevant circles of trade) and has commercial value because it is secret. The definition thus extends beyond more classic trade secrets like construction drawings or recipes, and may include negative information like known product defects or company code of conduct violations. (DLA, 2018)”

Protect trade secrets (V-Comply, 2017)

The unauthorized acquisition, use or disclosure of such secret information in a manner contrary to honest commercial practices by others is regarded as an unfair practice and a violation of the trade secret protection.

Case studies:

- Forever 21, Puma Settle Lawsuit over copies fancy footwear (TFL, 2018)
- Star Athletica, LLC vs. Varsity Brands, Inc. (US, 2017)

Fair use - means that you can use copyrighted materials without a license, only for few purposes (Ping, 2017):

- Commentary
- Criticism
- Reporting
- Research
- Teaching

Creative Commons – licenses free of charge

Illegal and harmful use of media

There is a whole range of rules which, for different reasons, limit the use and distribution of certain content. The infringement of these rules leads to the illegality of the content (EC, Illegal and harmful content on the Internet, 1996).

Several issues do not involve the protection of public order, but rather the protection of the rights of individuals. The below examples represent illegal and harmful aspects of using media.

Illegal aspects of using media. Source: (Carballo, 2018)

Guide questions:

- What issues do you see in the poster?
- Which one do you understand?
- Which one do you not know?
- What possible dangers are depicted in the picture?
- Which of these issues has happened to you or your friends? Why did they happen?

Ethical aspects

In the competitive world of media communications, media creators sometimes lose or neglect sight of the ethical implications of their work. All their products, media messages and advertisements contain explicit and implicit messages.

What shall we do: First, read or hear what is stated. This is the explicit message. Then look again critically and think about what they might be saying. The meaning might be different for each individual.

When you come across a media advertisement or message, you deconstruct it. You are using your reading and thinking strategies to understand the message.

Professional support (Garrett, 2020)

- Is the message playing off a stereotype?
- What are creators implying about their product?
- What are some other messages you get from looking at this?

- How will it make you feel?

Implicit and explicit messages are techniques used in various forms of media to influence and inform the audience. Sometimes, the creator may or may not intend to say certain messages, but they are there.

- Explicit messages are obvious, clear, specific and detailed.
- Implicit messages are hidden messages. This means the media uses visuals, settings, and body language to communicate meaning. These are messages transmitted, implied or understood though not directly expressed.

Example 1

This advertisement shows a mother holding a Swiffer WetJet to clean up after her kid who is making a mess. The ad explains how fast and easy it is to clean up messes when you use a Swiffer.

Implicit vs. explicit message, (Lewis, 2012)

Look at the poster and respond to the questions:

- What are the explicit messages contained? It is obvious that they are selling and promoting the “WetJet” cleaner which they are saying is doing its job very quickly.
- What is the implied message? Some people can understand that the role of women in life is to clean and take care of the household.
- Why might some people be angry about this? The stereotypical housewife can be offensive because the majority of the cooking and cleaning media product advertisements contain women using these products. The woman looks happy and looks like she enjoys cleaning up after her child using the Swiffer WetJet.

This advertisement is an example of a gender stereotype because it assumes that the mother would be the one cleaning up after the child and it shows her enjoying it thoroughly. Mothers are not the only ones who use the Swiffer and that is why this advertisement is a gender stereotype (MPBEISEL, 2014).

Example 2

This advertisement shows a mother cleaning and having her daughter close. The Mr. Clean ad wears a text message “This Mother’s Day, Get Back To The Job That Really Matters”.

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Gender stereotype message, (MPBEISEL, 2014)

Look at the poster and respond to the questions:

- What are the explicit messages contained?
- What is the implied message?
- Why might some people be angry about this?

This advertisement is another example of a gender stereotype. It seems like the only job women and mothers do that really matters is cleaning the house and cleaning up after their children and family while using Mr. Clean. (MPBEISEL, 2014).

Example 3

This advertisement shows a man wearing a hearing aid. The ad states that men never listen but with this hearing aid at least you will know they can hear you.

Gender stereotype message, (MPBEISEL, 2014)

Look at the poster and respond to the questions:

- What are the explicit messages contained?
- What is the implied message?
- Why might some people be angry about this?

This advertisement is a gender stereotype: it seems like the men never listen.

Stereotypes can affect individuals – generally: women, ethnic minorities, racial minorities, gays and lesbians.

Societal issues

Societal issues are major concerns that can affect large masses of people. There are seven societal challenges identified for Horizon 2020 strategy (Horizon, 2020).

- Health, demographic change and wellbeing;
- Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the bio-economy;
- Secure, clean and efficient energy;
- Smart, green and integrated transport;
- Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials;
- Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies;
- Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens.

Certainly, the challenges (not only societal challenges but in our case, societal) link people and even mobilize mass movements. With the advanced means of communication, media messages are rapidly spreading. The impact can be positive or negative.

Case study - Top Gear

A well-known and analyzed study is the one in which Top Gear Philippines wrongfully accused Mr. Nestor Punzalan as a suspect in a shooting incident.

The video shared by Top Gear in which a road rage turned into a shooting incident in Quiapo became viral on Facebook.

Dimension of media and the accusations of the masses made the family of the suspect (wrongly accused) to suffer and deactivate the Facebook accounts.

Source: (GMA-News, 2016) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VE8GHioR1YU>

News: July 25, 2016 –A jostle in the road between a car driver and cyclist led to a fist fight that ended in a gun shooting, leaving the cyclist dead at P. Casal Street in Quiapo, Manila. The suspect left the scene of the crime leaving the dead victim lying on the street.

Incident advertised by abs-cbn.com (Celis, 2016)

The editor of Top Gear Philippines has apologized for posting on its Facebook page a link to the social media account of the wrong person being linked to a fatal road rage incident in Quiapo, Manila. "I was responsible for posting the photo of Mr. Punzalan's vehicle, and I realize now that I shouldn't have done so. I accept full responsibility. This is all on me", Top Gear editor Vernon Sarne.

Also, social media was instrumental in the arrest of the suspect Vhon Tanto who admitted his crime.

Guide questions

Q1. How was Mr. Nestor Punzalan affected by being wrongfully accused in social media as the suspect in the said shooting incident?

ANSWERS

- "Mr. Punzalan immediately goes to the police station to clarify that he and his family are just wrongly accused in the shooting incident. Mr. Punzalan is afraid and gets angry because they have been bashed by the netizens in the incident that they did not do. Having this kind of incident that happens in Mr. Punzalan makes him and his family suffer from trauma that is caused by Cyber bullying. According to Vernon B. Sarne the editor of top gear Ph. That he was responsible for the mistaken incident that is posted on the said page. Sarne explained that he posted the wrong plate no. of the car which belongs to Mr. Punzalan that didn't do the shooting incident instead it is done by the Army reservist." (Tingan, Valdez, & Sabinay, 2018)
- "Mr. Nestor Punzalan got a lot of harsh criticisms and threats just because of that wrong accusation against him." (Lalaine, 2017)
- "Because of the wrong accuse to Mr. Punzalan, he was judged by the netizens as a killer and murderer and other people send him threats that will result to his anxiety and also may lead him to commit suicide." (Ruevick, 2017)

Q2. What is the liability of Top Gear, other media outlets, and netizens who wrongfully accused Mr. Nestor Punzalan as the suspect in the said shooting incident?

ANSWERS

- "Accusing someone with no such evidence or wrongly accusation with false evidence can lead and/or fall under the [Daez v. Court of Appeals, G.R. No. 47971, 31 October 1990, 191 SCRA 61, 67] or Libel case. Libel is defined as a public and malicious imputation of a crime, or vice or defect, real or imaginary, or any act, omission, condition, status or circumstance tending to discredit or cause the dishonour or contempt of a natural or juridical person or to blacken the memory of one who is dead.

Thus, the elements of libel are imputation of a discreditable act or condition to another; publication of the imputation, the identity of the person defamed; and, the existence of malice.” (Tingan, Valdez, & Sabinay, 2018)

- “As the source of the wrong information, Top Gear must apologize to Mr. Punzalan and take the responsibility for the mess they made.” (Lalaine, 2017)
- “All the netizens that have been sharing the wrong information should give an apology and stop the dissemination of wrong information so that the name of Mr. Punzalan will be clean in social media and to the people that have been already read the wrong information.” (Ruevick, 2017)

Q3. What role was played by citizen journalism and social media in this incident?

ANSWERS

- “First of all, citizen journalism has a huge involvement on this incident because of social media, they spread a news even though the news was faked like the post of top gear can shared people without knowing whether it is fake of truth according to Mr. Sarne he was responsible for posting Mr. Punzalan vehicle.” (Tingan, Valdez, & Sabinay, 2018)
- “Their role was being a source of the wrong information.” (Lalaine, 2017)
- “For me, the netizens were so active in terms of judging because they don’t even know if the information is true but they judged Mr. Punzalan in a wrong way without knowing if the information that they have been reading is true. They don’t even think also what will happen to Mr. Punzalan after this wrong accusation and threatening him in a wrong way.” (Ruevick, 2017)

Q4. What positive and negative effects of media and information on individuals and society were evident in this incident?

ANSWERS

- “The negative effect of media and information for every individual is when the message is posted on social media and when it is fake it’s immediately spread. The positive is you will also know the truth on social media. Like the post of the editor and chief of top gear, according to Vernon B. Sarne he accused Mr. Punzalan based on the testimony of the witness, which is wrong. He posts on social media this kind of news without critical thinking but through social media, the issue was fixed because of the apology of Mr. Vernon B. Sarne. According to the post of the editor of top gear that Mr. Punzalan has the primary suspect of the shooting incident and it is negative because he accused Mr. Punzalan without analysing the story behind it. The positive side is that after Mr. Sarne realized his post was fake, he admitted his mistake and made an online apology for Mr. Punzalan.” (Tingan, Valdez, & Sabinay, 2018)
- “The positive effects are everybody could share and easily access to the information but the negative is that not every information posted is reliable.” (Lalaine, 2017)
- “Because of having high-technology, the netizens can easily disseminate information in just a while or a minute but they don’t consider the factuality of the news even if it came from a group of people but we should always know if they are really a new caster.” (Ruevick, 2017)

Q5. How can we prevent this kind of incident as experienced by Mr. Punzalan from happening in the future?

ANSWERS

- “This kind of incident can be prevented by having critical thinking to the news posted on social media and avoid sharing and spreading it without knowing the story behind it. According to Francis Bacon (1605), the critical thing is the desire to seek, patience to doubt, fondness to meditate, slowness to assert, reediness to consider, carefulness to dispose and set in order; and hatred for every kind of imposture. So, we should have critical thinking in this kind of moment to avoid the mistaken identity.” (Tingan, Valdez, & Sabinay, 2018)

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- “As a netizen, I will only share the information that I am really sure of and have a solid proof.” (Lalaine, 2017)
- “I think we should always be careful in terms of sharing information especially if this information deals with court cases and too much risk and always remember that THINK BEFORE YOU CLICK”. (Ruevick, 2017)

Q6. What important lessons can we learn from this event as social media users?

ANSWERS

- “The important lesson we can learn about this incident is that when we encounter this kind of news posted on social media, we need to analyse hundred times or even thousands of times. That is because when we share the message or post on social media there are chances that the post we shared might be fake. Mr. Punzalan was wrongfully accused by Top Gear without analysing the news.” (Tingan, Valdez, & Sabinay, 2018)
- “As a social media user, we shouldn’t post anything without thinking carefully about it and be vigilant with false information.” (Lalaine, 2017)
- “Don’t be too greedy in terms of sharing information and don’t be too judgmental because not all of the information that we can get in social media is real/true, some of it can be fake. Before you share it with others, make sure that you evaluate and analyse if the source was given by the real authority to avoid some trouble.” (Ruevick, 2017)

Exercise 3: What is said and what is transmitted

Objectives:

- Understand the idea that media products may have both explicit and implicit messages
- Identify implicit messages in a media text

Duration: 10-15 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper, poster,

Methods: identify bias, search, discussion with peers

Description of the exercise: During this exercise, trainees are required to read the poster carefully and identify the explicit and implicit messages. The explicit messages are presented as examples.

Implicit and explicit messages, (Lewis, 2012)

Tasks:

- What are the explicit messages contained?
- Congratulations to the previous winners (Audi, BMW).
- Announce that in 2006, they (Subaru) are the winners.
- You can add here:
- What is the implied message?
- Write your answer here.
- Why might some people be angry about this?
- Write your answer here.
- Present the findings to your colleagues.

Debriefing:

- What questions did you ask yourself as you viewed this poster?
- In your opinion, how effective were the producers in communicating their message?

Lessons learned: Almost all messages and ads have explicit and implicit messages. Implicit messages depend on individual understanding of the subject/topic.

Recommendations: Look critically to understand what the creator wanted to implicitly transmit.

Forum

Objectives:

- Identify implicit messages in a media text
- Structure the content and ideas
- Give feedback

You are looking at the poster advertising GotMilk (<https://www.gotmilk.com/>). The explicit message is obvious. Is this the only message? Of course not. Which might be the implicit message?

Got milk campaign, (<https://www.gotmilk.com/>)

Tasks:

- Share your understanding of the implicit message via the forum
- Reply/ comments twice to your colleagues

Supplementary reading

Carballo, R. (2018). Legal, Ethical, and Societal Issues in Media and Information Literacy.

<https://bamil786447613.wordpress.com/2018/10/01/legal-ethical-and-societal-issues-in-media-and-information-literacy/>

4. Module 4 - Media and information literate individual

Upon completing this module, you will be able to:

- Understand how media messages are constructed
- Deconstruct media messages
- Produce media and information content
- Comprehend how manipulative information and media is /are formally and informally produced, organized, and disseminated

Media messages are everywhere: on your mobile phone, on your computer screen, in the newspapers and magazines, on TV, broadcasted through radio waves. All these mediated messages are carefully prepared to transmit their message. With so many viewpoints, and so many messages it is hard to separate fact from fiction. To guide us in our daily exploration, several education institutes developed core concepts of the media that surround us. The Center for Media Literacy developed core concepts and principles (OME, 1989), (YALI, 2020).

Key principles of media

As media and information literate individuals, we need to know the principles of media:

Media messages are constructions

When we say that all media messages are constructed, we mean that all media messages have been assembled by someone. That “someone” could be a single person, or it could be a large organization. The messages and values embedded in this particular piece of media are those of the people who have created it (MLB, 2020).

Ex. Media messages for food include Media Smart (MediaSmart, 2020):

- | | | |
|---|-------------------|---------------------------|
| • Logo | • Slogan | • Nutritional information |
| • Image of the product | • Mascot (if any) | • Contest (if any) |
| • Images of other food along with the main product (e.g. fruit) | • Other images | • Premium |
| | • Ingredients | • Health claims |

Source: (ClickAmericana, 2020)

Thus, media products are never entirely accurate reflections of the real world, but we perceive many media products as direct representations of what is real.

- In adds, there are expert teams that choose about what to include, what to leave out and how to present what is included
- In documentary films, producers decide what to cut
- In photographs, the photographer's own vision of what she wants to show within the frame demonstrates her own values and beliefs.
- A newspaper writer's articles may be based on his own beliefs or based on the beliefs and ideologies of his publishers.

Constructed message (Bermey, 2014)

Critical thinking:

- Who has created this media product?
- What is its purpose?
- What assumptions or beliefs do its creators have that are reflected in the content?

Audiences negotiate meanings

The meaning of any media product is not created solely by its producers but is, instead, a collaboration between them and the audience – which means that different audiences can take away different meanings from the same product. Media literacy encourages us to understand how individual factors, such as age, gender, race and social status affect our interpretations of media.

E.g.

One example is the Academy Award-winning film, *Slumdog Millionaire*. *Slumdog Millionaire* is about a young boy named Jamal Malik from the Slums of Mumbai, India that gets a chance to take part in the game show, *Who Wants to be a Millionaire?* Jamal Malik wins the gameshow, along with 20 million Rupees. While Jamal is waiting to answer the 20-million-rupee question, he asks the host, "Are you nervous?" This is a key quote in the film because the host makes fun of Malik on the show because he is a slum dweller, and when he asks this question, it shows that Jamal is a strong young man.

Slumdog Millionaire Trailer, <https://youtu.be/kuSTr48P9mc> (YouTube, 2012)

When the movie was released, the North American audience thought that the movie was fantastic, and it made millions at the box office. In India, however, the feedback was not so great. The Indian people felt that their nation was being shown negatively, with the slums and police corruption being major parts of the film. At Indian cinemas, only 25 to 50% of the seats were occupied. The Indian people were mad about the way that their nation was being portrayed in this movie because North Americans and other audiences would think of the negative connotations in the film when they heard about the slums and India. (WillGregg, 2012)

Critical thinking:

- How might different people see this media product differently?
- How does this make you feel, based on how similar or different you are from the people portrayed in the media product?

Media have commercial implications

We should know that most media productions are businesses. Consequently, they have to make a profit. We need to understand the economic basis of media production, how it impinges on content, techniques, and distribution (OME, 1989).

Media producers portray what the customer (those that they target) wants to see so that they will invest in their products. The media place their products very carefully to attract the right type of consumer for their product.

Commercial implications (Bermey, 2014)

Usually, media industries belong to a powerful network of corporations that exert influence on content and distribution. E.g.

- The television industry - all programs, news, public affairs, or entertainment - must be judged by the size of the audience they generate.
- YouTube videos and Facebook posts (where media content is not made for profit) – how content is distributed are nearly always run with profit in mind.

Critical thinking:

- What is the commercial purpose of this media product (in other words, how will it help someone make money)?
- How does this influence the content and how it is communicated?
- If no commercial purpose can be found, what other purposes might the media product have (for instance, to get attention for its creator or to convince audiences of a particular point of view)?
- How do those purposes influence the content and how it is communicated?

Media have social and political implications

Media convey ideological messages about values, power and authority. In media literacy, what or who is absent may be more important than what or who is included.

Media messages may be the result of conscious decisions, but more often, they are the result of unconscious biases and unquestioned assumptions – and they can have a significant influence on what we think and believe. Media have a great influence on politics and on forming social change (Zúñiga & Chen, 2019). E.g.

- The significant role of digital media in shaping diverse forms of political participation and mobilizing large-scale social protests around the world.
- Twitter and Facebook provide a platform for cognitive, affective and behavioural connections that enable people to network collaboratively.
- Digital media provide people with news and mobilizing information and allow them to exchange their opinions with many others, motivating them to engage in public activities.
- Online social networks influence the type and amount of information to which people are exposed. Social media platforms curate content based on algorithmic information sorting, which elicits critical issues that affect the development of the democratic process.
- TV news coverage and advertising can greatly influence the election of a national leader based on image.
- Representations of world issues, both in journalism and fiction, can affect how much attention they receive.

E.g.

<p>News topic</p> <p>COVID-19 Vaccine Distribution Continues, Alongside Concerns About Access <i>Headline Roundup December 29th, 2020</i></p> <p>The U.S. has reportedly administered over 2 million doses of COVID-19 coronavirus vaccines as of Tuesday, roughly three weeks after the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved the first vaccines for emergency use.</p>		
<p>... from the Left</p> <p>Biden Slams Trump for Slow COVID-19 Vaccine Rollout</p> <p>Several red states are eschewing federal recommendations for vaccine distribution and prioritizing the elderly and vulnerable over essential workers, in the hopes of saving more lives. [...] That is a different distribution plan than the one recommended in mid-December by the federal Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices</p> <p><i>Washington Examiner</i> 29 December 2020 by David Hogberg</p>		

Don't be fooled by media bias and fake news. Source: (AllSlides, 2020)

Critical thinking:

- Who and what is shown in a positive light? In a negative light?
- Why might these people and things be shown this way?
- Who and what is not shown at all?
- What conclusions might audiences draw based on these facts?

Each medium has a unique aesthetic form

The content of media depends partially on the nature of the medium. This includes the technical, commercial and storytelling demands of each medium: for instance, the interactive nature of video games leads to different forms of storytelling – and different demands on media creators – that are found in film and TV.

The media use several different ways to get consumers' attention without them even realizing it (Bermey, 2014). E.g.

- Different camera angles or lighting can make a consumer more likely to purchase a product.
- Some kids buy certain brands just for the brand name, like Nike or Adidas. There is nothing that special about those brands, but just because tons of people have them, the consumer may be tempted to buy them as well.
- On TV advertisements, people always show the ideal reality, with everything being peaceful, rather than what reality is like.
- Subliminal messages are visual or auditory stimuli that the conscious mind cannot perceive, often inserted into other media such as TV commercials or songs. This kind of messaging can be used to strengthen or heighten the persuasiveness of advertisements, or to convey an altogether different message entirely (Wordstream, 2017).

Example 1. Subliminal messages

Take a look at the picture below. What do you see?

Source: (Turismoassociati, 2014)

If you're like most people, you probably see some weird-looking flowers. Maybe you notice the bumblebee in the corner or a small blue bird sitting on a petal (Dallett, 2014). Your eyes are taking in visual information and telling your brain, "We see some weird-looking flowers."

- Now look again and focus on the lower half of the image. See anything else?
- How about the letters S-E-X?

The practice of placing hidden (subliminal) words in select print advertisements is a technique used by advertisers. Advertisers know that most people will not spend much time looking at print advertisements. Therefore, hidden words, ideas, and imagery can be placed in print advertisements without immediate detection (DarkSide, 2013).

Source: (DarkSide, 2013)

“If there's one thing that every marketing and advertising pro retained from Business 101 class, it's that sex sells.” - Emily Friedman

Example 2. Happy family

In 2011, Coca-Cola launched a campaign aiming at linking the brand portfolio to family mealtimes. The ads for radio, TV and outdoor feature carried the messages “Saturday night tastes better with Coca-Cola and ITV1” and “meals taste better with Coca-Cola”.

Source: (O'Reilly, 2011)

“Celebrating the role of the Coca-Cola family at mealtimes, the activity showcases the brands as an enhancer of happiness, helping to bring families together to share precious moments.” - Zoe Howorth, market director

Critical thinking:

- What techniques does the media product use to get your attention and to communicate its message?
- In what ways are the images in the media product manipulated through various techniques (for example lighting, makeup, camera angle, photo manipulation)?
- What are the expectations of the genre (for example print advertising, TV drama, music video) towards its subject?

Everyone sees messages differently, depending on how they were raised and what experiences they have gone through in life. Understanding its origins can help you discover more about what the main message is.

Common purposes of media

The majority of the media are made to do more than one thing (MediaSmart, 2020). Below you can see depicted the most common purposes:

- **To entertain (funny, exciting content).** Sometimes the best way to engage a large audience is through humour or an interesting story. Geico (insurance company, case study below) is a perfect example of a company that tries to entertain through its advertising.
- **To educate or inform (teaching content, giving information).** When media is used to educate and inform, it can be extremely powerful. This is often the first step for advertisers. Before people will buy your product or service, people must understand what it is and how the product or service can improve their life.
- **To advertise (content that tries to make you want to buy).** This may mean to convince a person to buy something, as in the case of advertising, or this may simply be to make a person feel or think in a certain way. Advertisers spend a lot of time trying to make audiences feel like this about a business's brand.
- **To persuade (make you agree on an idea).** This is often used together with advertising scope (commercial), trying to persuade the audience to buy. Sometimes, the companies use media messages to enlighten the audience about the current situation.

Are you wondering how the creators do this? Well, there are several media vehicles used to transmit the messages. The creators appeal to those techniques, which make our brain react better in different situations.

Content marketing matrix, Source: (SuperDream, 2020)

Case study – Market positioning

Geico is a reputable insurance company with low rates.

This is a perfect example of why positioning matters (Calkins, 2013). Why buy from Geico? To save money. This is the core of the brand. Geico does not promise the best service or the most complete coverage. It promises low rates. With this clear positioning, Geico is free to be creative. It develops catchy ad campaigns and funds high impact marketing efforts.

People struggle to settle on a clear positioning. Geico shows that having one is the foundation of great marketing.

Watch the video: NBA Dikembe Mutombo GEICO Commercial [Here](#)

NBA Dikembe Mutombo GEICO Commercial (no no no not in my house)
1,512,404 views · Mar 19, 2013

15K 222 SHARE SAVE ...

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RtXtOuxBuvQ&list=PL3XFuCC7f2monu5Gp7oDsjm5NfEuQRLX>

Source: (Geico.com, 2013)

From the video:

- The slogan “happier than Dikembe Mutombo blocking a shot.”
- The logo and geico.com.
- This commercial destroys all shot attempts and gains 1,983,594 views on YouTube.

Analyze carefully the video and then answer the questions:

- What is the main scope of the advertisement?
- How do they act?

Expert opinion: The comedy and lack of issue-relevant argument make peripheral processing the elaboration of choice. Incongruity-resolution is the only process within the commercial that makes the humour type comic wit. Incongruity is viewed when people keep trying to put something into a basket of some way shape or form and it gets blocked by Dikembe Mutombo, a great shot blocker. Resolution is found when the audience realizes this is what brings him a lot of joy. The theme of happiness through Dikembe’s example and associating that with Geico’s customers makes this commercial have semantic relatedness. (Davis, 2013)

Professional support

We are aware of the construction of media messages. What about deconstructing them? Professionals recommend a set of questions that can guide us (Tingan, Valdez, & Sabinay, 2018)

1. Whose message for this? Who created or paid for it? The bear brand company.
2. Who is the “target audience”? What is their age, ethnicity, class, profession, interest, etc.? What words, image or sound suggest this. The target audience is the all-father worker the “lakas tibay” there indicate on their product.

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3. What is the “text” of the message? (What we actually see and/or hear: written spoken words, photos, drawing, logos, design, music, sound, etc.) The “lakas tibay” they want to know even they arrived from work they still a quality time for their child.
4. What is the “subtext” of the message? (What do you think is the hidden or unstated meaning?)
5. What kind of lifestyle is presented? Is it glamorized or how? The hardworking father.
6. What values are expressed? The free can give for his child even after his work.
7. What positive messages are presented? What negative messages are presented? The positive message is bonding between father and child. The negative message is nothing because the message is all positive.
8. What group of people does this message empower? What group does it disempower? How does this serve the media makers interests? The group of fathers who work for their family.
9. What part of the story is not being told? The bonding of father and mother.

Exercise 4: Deconstruct messages

Objectives:

- Understand the content of the message
- Ability to deconstruct messages constructively
- Evaluate a creative text/visual/audio-based presentation using design principle and elements

Duration: 15 min

Tools: message, pen, questionnaire

Methods: evaluation, storyboard

Description of the exercise: Look at the poster and deconstruct messages by answering the questions.

The below advertisement targets families. In this Skechers advertisement, they show a happy family where each member is wearing a pair of sketchers. These types of ads portray the family as happy because they are wearing the Skechers product. In addition, this ad for Skechers has a line at the bottom of the page stating "Skechers joins Brooke Burke and family in their support of the cedar women's Cancer Research".

Source: (Pamela, 2016)

Tasks: investigate the poster and deconstruct the message by answering:

- Whose message is this? Who created it or who paid for it?
- Who is the “target audience”? What is their age, ethnicity, class, profession, interest, etc? What words, image or sound suggest this?
- What is the “text” of the message? (What we actually see and/or hear: written spoken words, photos, drawing, logos, design, music, sound, etc.)
- What is the “subtext” of the message? (What do you think is the hidden or unstated meaning?)
- What kind of lifestyle is presented? Is it glamorized or how?
- What values are expressed?
- What positive messages are presented? What negative messages are presented?
- What group of people does this message empower? What group does it disempower? How does this serve the media makers’ interests?

Debriefing: Can you identify a part of the story that is not being told? What is your opinion?

In the ad, the family pictured is the Burke's and it is showing that they both support cancer research, and all are wearing Skechers. People who are viewing this ad will be supportive of the Burke's for donating to cancer research and will be more compelled to purchase Skechers since they associate

with such a good cause. People who also have donated towards cancer funding can feel a sense of connection towards Skechers. Furthermore, this ad shows the ideal "perfect family" where everyone is smiling and close together. The family is all connected and it is obvious they love each other very much. Since they are all wearing sketchers, people will buy them for themselves and their family members in hopes to create their own "perfect family. –Amy (Pamela, 2016)

Lessons learned: Even if there is not a link between the product and the value expressed, the ad creator creates that link.

Recommendations: Look carefully, analyze critically and make decisions rationally.

Forum

Objectives:

- Product media and information content
- Structure the content and ideas
- Give feedback

You are required to create an advertisement for your college/ school/ university. Promote it using what you have learnt and upload it for your colleagues in the forum.

Tasks:

- Share your thought about the stories created by your colleagues via the forum
- Reply/ comments twice to your colleagues

Supplementary reading

Davis, P. (2013). Fifteen Percent or More: A Content Analysis of Geico's Commercial Advertising.
<https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1262&context=masters>

5. Module 5 - Dimensions of media

Upon completing this module, you will be able to:

- Describe the different dimensions of media and information
- Evaluate the reliability and validity of manipulative media and information and its sources
- Assess information sources against reliability, validity, accuracy, authority, timeliness, and Points of view or biases among several evaluation criteria

Types of media

Certainly, the dimensions of media are unimaginable: several formats, multiple channels, manipulative content and many more factors that can characterize it. Researchers classified media from various points of view:

By types of media (BBA, 2020)

- Print (books, newsletter, magazines, journals, and other printed materials)
- Broadcast (radio, television, and film)
- Outdoor or Out of Home OOH Media
- New Media (internet)

By Media and Information Sources

- Indigenous
- Library
- Internet
- Others/ Mass Media

Advantages and disadvantages of media

Pros and cons of print media (OnePitch, 2020)

The Pros

- Established history - Print media is still a widely trusted resource for relevant and fact-checked information. Having your story published in print can mean a reputation boost.
- People are looking for you - As found by the Readership Institute at Northwestern University, advertising is one of the BIGGEST selling points for printed media purchases. People LOVE reading magazine advertisements.
- Targeted audiences - As long as you reach out to publications that fit your industry, you'll know only ideal audiences will be seeing your content.

The Cons

- May not be around forever - While still widely circulated, digital media makes it so easy and affordable to publish content. Hence, print media may fade away.
- Bad for the environment - Paper has detrimental impacts on the environment. In the wake of climate change and wildfires in Australia and the Amazon, audiences are looking for greener ways of ingesting content.
- Easy to get overlooked - Since printed media is jam-packed with advertising, it can be easy for you to get lost- especially if it's competing with more prominent brands.

Pros and cons of print broadcast (OnePitch, 2020)

The Pros

- Massive audience reach - Over 95% of US homes have televisions, and 93% of adults still listen to the radio.
- Trusted media outlets - Just like printed media, broadcast media hosts respected programs and personalities that people turn to religiously.
- Accessible to TV, computing, and mobile - Even though broadcast media centres around television and radio, most TV and radio stations have an online presence. Thanks to platforms like Netflix and Hulu, as well as podcasts, broadcast media is transient.

The Cons

- Expensive - It takes a pretty penny to secure a spot on prime-time television and radio.
- Difficult to get your foot in the door - It's competitive and challenging to get the attention of decision-makers. It might be harder for new companies without street-cred to get featured.
- Dying medium - Broadcast media is giving way to digital media as mobile devices are more affordable and accessible.

Pros and cons of outdoor advertising (BBA, 2020)

The Pros

- Geographic flexibility
- Continuity – Helps to remind clients
- Efficient and cheap – It can generate considerable reach and frequency level at a low cost
- Flexible and creative impact – It includes billboards, boarding, neon sign posters

The Cons

- Limited message
- Wastage in terms of coverage
- Limited effectiveness
- Public criticism

Pros and cons of digital mass media (WU, 2020)

The Pros

- It Can Keep Us Connected - For instance, when a tsunami strikes, people all over the world hear about it within moments and can mobilize immediately to help. Without mass media, we would have far less ability to understand how we're all connected and how we all need each other.
- It Can Spur Business - Thanks to the business communication made possible by mass media, businesses can reach potential consumers faster and easier than ever before. This helps keep our economy going.
- It Can Spread Art and Culture - On the internet, you can see all of the world's artistic masterpieces or learn about the particularities of a culture far removed from your own. In addition, numerous TV and radio programs devote themselves to exploring the world, offering us the chance to discover new things and new ideas, and enlighten ourselves in the process.
- It Can Give Voice to the Voiceless - From reporters bringing us stories of people in difficult situations to social media allowing one person's thoughts to go viral and spread across the world, mass media can lift an individual voice that would otherwise have gone unheard.

The Cons

- It Can Empower the Already Powerful - While mass media can create opportunities for anyone to share their story, the vast majority of our mass media is bought. And because it's bought, those with money can deeply influence what we see and hear. This gives the rich—and those connected to the rich—a far louder voice than the rest of us. At its best, this is unfair. At its worst, it's a way for a tiny minority to seize power over the vast majority.
- It Can Be Used for Disinformation and Hate - How do you know what you're seeing or hearing from mass media is true? While some sources of information are far more trustworthy than others, mass

media as a whole is vulnerable to propaganda and its lies. Totalitarian regimes have used mass media for nearly a century to control what their people believe. With the rise of the internet, even those in democracies can be easily exposed to media designed to drive us to hate or believe in lies.

- It Can Homogenize Culture - Before mass media, art and culture were more localized, so they reflected diversity in how people spoke, dressed, and entertained themselves. Now, the entire world often sees and hears the same cultural influences. While diversity still clearly exists, there is the risk that mass media might reduce cultural variety, leaving us with less art and fewer inspirations.
- It Can Overtake Personal Connections - We've all seen it or been a part of it: a group having dinner where everyone spends much of the evening staring at their phones or gazing at a TV in the corner. As much as mass media can connect us with people all over the world, it can disconnect us from the people right in front of us.
- Constantly changing but never forgetful - It's challenging to stay ahead of technology, platforms, and trend evolutions. Not to mention, whatever you put on the internet stays there.

CRAAP criteria

Manipulative media can be both traditional and digital. The use of manipulative media in the classroom is essential since it gives a concrete experience for the learners because students can explore and investigate. Thus, manipulative media is a very important tool in learning since it involves kids in learning, this stimulates a lot of senses, which produces better learning retention (MIL, 2020b). But manipulative media can also be dangerous.

Not all media sources are equally valuable or reliable. Critically evaluating the information you find is central to your career as well as your daily life. Determining the credibility of the information you find is not always easy - think of the following criteria during evaluation (Blakeslee, 2004). Librarians at California State University, Chico proposed a 5 indicators test for source evaluation: the CRAAP Test.

- Currency: The timeliness of the information.
- Relevance: The depth and importance of the information.
- Authority: The source of the information.
- Accuracy: The reliability of the information.
- Purpose: The possible bias present in the information.

CRAAP, Source: LibGuide, 2020

Professional support

Determining the effectiveness, authority, and credibility of a source may be a difficult task. Experts from Librarian guides recommend a set of guide questions (GuidesLib, 2020).

CURRENCY: Some material can quickly become outdated. Websites fall out of use, are no longer maintained, or disappear altogether. The following criteria will help you judge the currency of a website:

- Is there a date of publication or last update?
- When was the page created?
- Do the links work?
- Is the page maintained regularly?
- Is the information considered current for your topic/research?

RELEVANCE: There is so much information out there, it is easy to get sidetracked or bogged down. Keeping focused and on-topic makes deciding on the relevance of sources an easier task.

- Does the information relate to your topic or answer your question?
- Who is the intended audience and is the information at an appropriate level (not too basic or advanced) for your needs?
- Does the resource claim to be comprehensive and how does it meet those claims?
- Have you looked at a variety of sources before determining this is one you will use?
- Why is this resource preferable to other resource types or formats?

AUTHORITY: Anyone can publish information on the internet. This does not mean they are qualified experts in the field. The following questions will help decide if the website is an authoritative source:

- Who is the author of the page?
- What are their credentials?
- What institution are they affiliated with?
- Is that producing institution reputable?
- Is there an email address or other contact information?
- What does the domain name tell you about the source?

ACCURACY: There are no regulations, standards, or systems in place to ensure that information on the web is correct. Judging the accuracy of information is important when utilizing internet resources.

- Is the information correct?
- Can it be verified from other sources?
- Is the information cited?
- Are there spelling, grammatical, or typographical errors?
- Has the information been refereed/peer-reviewed?

PURPOSE: It should be clear why the information on the website is being made available. Knowing and understanding the purpose of information is key to conducting high-quality research.

- Is this information meant to teach? Inform? Persuade? Entertain?
- Do the authors/sponsors make their intentions or purpose clear?
- Is the information fact? Opinion? Propaganda?
- What other websites are linked to this one?
- Is there advertising on the site? What is being advertised?
- Does the point of view appear objective and impartial?
- Are there political, ideological, cultural, religious, institutional, or personal biases?

Case study – One size does not fit all

Finding information today is easy; it is all around you. Making sure the information you find is reliable can be a challenge. When you use Google or any social media to get your information, how do you know it can be trusted?

Make sure the sources that you use for gathering information pass the CRAAP criteria.

Currency: The timeliness of the information

The screenshot shows a LibGuide article titled "Police Misconduct" dated April 6, 2012. A green callout bubble points to the date, stating "This topic has evolved since the 2012 publication date". The article title is "Will excessive force, racial profiling be curbed?" by Kenneth Jost. The introduction discusses the U.S. Department of Justice's oversight of local police departments. An "ISSUE TRACKER for Related Reports" sidebar lists several related articles from 2012 to 2016, including "Jailing Debtors", "Crime and Police Conduct", "Police Tactics", and "Police Misconduct".

Source: (LibGuide, 2020)

This report is dated 2012. This is not Pass or Fail. The information would likely still be valuable for background information, but consulting more current sources is essential.

Relevance: The depth and importance of the information

The screenshot shows a LibGuide "Sample Assignment" section. A green callout bubble above the text says "Key Clues". The assignment text is: "Write a focused, well-organized, well-supported research essay that evaluates a technological innovation described in our text book. Your essay should provide an overall argument based on researching the benefits and drawbacks that this future technology might bring. Overall, will potential benefits outweigh possible drawbacks, or is it the other way around? Why?"

Source: (LibGuide, 2020)

At this stage, it is crucial to know and understand what you are looking for. This will trigger the response to relevance criteria.

Accuracy: The reliability of the information

The image shows a screenshot of a medical journal article. The article title is "Ileal-lymphoid-nodular hyperplasia, non-specific colitis, and pervasive developmental disorder in children". The authors listed are A J Wakefield, S H Murch, A Anthony, J Linnell, D M Casson, M Malik, M Berelowitz, A P Dhillon, M A Thomson, P Harvey, A Valentine, S E Davies, and J A Walker-Smith. The article is divided into sections: Summary, Introduction, Patients and methods, and Clinical investigations. A green callout bubble on the right side of the article contains the text "Looks can be deceiving".

Source: (LibGuide, 2020)

Even though the article looks super useful and authoritative, be careful. This article reports original research proving that there is a link between childhood vaccinations and autism. Do not stop with one single source.

Authority: The source of the information

The image shows a screenshot of a news article from SFGATE. The article title is "UCLA researchers warn centuries of drought could return to California". The author is listed as "By Bill D'Arbore" and the article was updated on Tuesday, September 20, 2016. A green callout bubble with a pointer to the author's name contains the text "Article Author".

Source: (LibGuide, 2020)

Most credible articles on the Web include the author's name. Google the name to learn more about the person and their qualifications. If there is a website, then the organization acts as an author or publisher. In this situation, look for the "About Us" section of the website.

Purpose: The possible bias presented in the information

The screenshot shows the 'About Heritage' section of the Heritage Foundation website. A green callout bubble with a black arrow points to the text: 'Describes their purpose as an organization'. The text on the website states: 'Founded in 1973, The Heritage Foundation is a research and educational institution—a think tank—whose mission is to formulate and promote conservative public policies based on the principles of free enterprise, limited government, individual freedom, traditional American values, and a strong national defense.'

Source: (LibGuide, 2020)

Read the About section of the Web site. Not all organizations are as forthcoming about their perspective and biases. Sometimes, the language reveals the real purpose of subtly persuading you to accept their point of view or bias.

Expert opinion: Misleading or false information abounds and can catch you unawares because you find it in places you visit all the time like Facebook, Google, Twitter, or other sources. In fact, you may get this information from sources you trust (LibGuide, 2020).

Exercise 5: Website evaluation

Objective:

- Analyse the website with CRAAP

Duration: 20 minutes

Tools: website, internet

Methods: evaluation,

Description of the exercise: Many pages may seem reliable at first, but as you evaluate them, you may find that they are less than credible sources. By looking for clues on different parts of a webpage, you can decide whether it is reliable. As you practice this skill, you will be able to evaluate web pages more quickly and accurately.

The next page presents an example of a website.

This exercise introduces you to the evaluation of a website. Ask yourself a few key questions.

Tasks:

- When was the information gathered and posted or published?
- Does the information help you understand your topic better?
- Who wrote the article?
- Are claims backed up with reliable sources?
- Does the website show bias?
- If they cite a scientific study, does the study sound credible?

Debriefing: There is clearly a problem with this article, as it seems that the author has fabricated information to get people to buy K-Power Energy Bars. While these energy bars may be a quality product, you probably should not believe anything the article says about vitamin K or Caribbean Hibiscus root. Although the article is partially true and cites credible sources, it would be best to go directly to those sources to get more trustworthy information. Overall, this article is probably not objective or reliable.

Lessons learned: Just because a website looks scientific or historical does not mean it's credible.

Recommendation: Unless the information can be verified, it may be all made up, so take your time whenever you evaluate online information.

K-POWER[®] Energy Bars

About Us Products Testimonials Help Log In

K-Power Store

New Products
K-Power
K-Power Xtreme
K-Power Shake
Biotin Blast
Trail Mix

Gift Cards
My Account

Unlocking the Power of Vitamin K

by Dr. Kay Powerton

Your body needs many different types of vitamins and minerals in order to stay healthy. One of the most overlooked vitamins is vitamin K. The main purpose of vitamin K is to allow blood to clot if you get an injury⁽¹⁾. However, it may also help to keep your bones strong⁽²⁾ and protect against Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma⁽³⁾.

The best sources of vitamin K are vegetables - especially leafy greens. Kale, turnip greens, spinach, and broccoli are all excellent sources. Therefore, by including these vegetables in your diet, you should get enough vitamin K, right?

Wrong! Although most people eat plenty of these foods, most of the vitamin K is not absorbed by the body. As a result, vitamin K deficiency is extremely common in adults.

Luckily, there is a way to unlock the power of vitamin K, which allows your body to receive its full benefits. This secret has been known for thousands of years, but scientists are just now rediscovering it. I'm going to tell you what this secret is, but I'll start by telling you a story.

When Christopher Columbus sailed to the New World in 1492, the Native Americans showed him many plants, animals, and foods that he had never seen before. But one thing in particular caught his attention: The natives often made a soup that consisted of leafy greens (possibly kale) along with the root of the hibiscus plant, which was first ground into a fine paste. Columbus noted in his journal that the soup was "delicious," but he noticed something even more remarkable about it: He always felt refreshed after eating it, and it also seemed to make wounds heal more quickly.

Columbus was eager to bring this "miraculous" soup back to Europe, so he loaded several hibiscus plants onto his ships for the return journey. When he arrived home, he attempted to make the soup, but he found that it had lost its miraculous qualities. He correctly deduced the reason for this: The tropical climate and the rich, sandy soils of the Caribbean greatly increased the potency of the hibiscus roots. As a result, the soup did not catch on in Europe, and it was eventually forgotten.

Scientists now understand that Caribbean Hibiscus root contains special compounds that unlock the power of vitamin K. In fact, no other hibiscus root in the world has this quality. Many leading nutritionists recommend eating Caribbean Hibiscus root along with leafy greens. One of the easiest ways to do this is to eat K-Power Energy Bars, which contain kale and Caribbean Hibiscus root. Each bar contains enough vitamin K to last you through the day, and the Caribbean Hibiscus root ensures that all of the vitamin K is absorbed by your body.

A study conducted in 2012 found that while many energy bars contain vitamin K, only K-Power Energy Bars allow your body to absorb it.

As you can see, eating an energy bar from one of the other leading brands won't benefit your body nearly as much as a K-Power Energy Bar. Furthermore, the unabsorbed vitamin K could actually harm your body. That's why athletes always choose K-Power Energy Bars - the bar that helps you run faster, jump higher, and quickly recover from injuries.

References:

1. <http://www.mayoclinic.com/health/drug-information/DR602165>
2. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11684396>
3. <http://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2010/04/100419151117.htm>

Source: (Goodwill, 2020)

Erasmus+

ATHENS
LIFELONG
LEARNING
INSTITUTE

SEAL
CYPRUS

Forum

Objectives:

- Evaluate a webpage
- Give feedback

Look carefully at the website. Analyze each part and then answer the following questions:

- Are there any funny or exciting things? Why is it entertainment?
- How is the website educational? Does it use good evidence to support its claims?
- What is advertising?
- Do they want to persuade? Who created it? How do you know? Why do you think it is persuasive?
- Is there a main scope of the website? Which one?

Tasks:

- Share your results with your colleagues via the forum
- Reply/ comments twice to your colleagues

Supplementary reading

- Walden University (2020). The pros and cons of mass media.

<https://www.waldenu.edu/online-bachelors-programs/bs-in-communication/resource/the-pros-and-cons-of-mass-media>

6. Assessment quizzes

Module 1

- 1) Which of the following best describes “media”?
 - a) Social networks and online communication that easily spread messages
 - b) Music, movies, TV, radio, newspapers, video games, magazines, photos, text messages, brand logos on clothes
 - c) Photos and videos shared online with explicit text messages

- 2) How can media literacy skills help you?
 - a) I will show more empathy in relation to media messages of other netizens
 - b) I will be able to analyse and evaluate media messages in a critical way
 - c) I will spread all the media messages so that all people are informed about various issues

- 3) Which of the following is part of the role of the media in a democratic society?
 - a) Informing the public about democratic choices by clarifying complex issues
 - b) Keeping the public away from abuses that can disrupt their daily routine
 - c) Mobilizing public opinion for political issues, rather than for humanitarian causes

- 4) What does it mean to be a smart consumer of information?
 - a) Using marketing techniques to sell products to smart consumers
 - b) Exposing information in such a media format to help the information consumer decide if the messages make sense
 - c) Determining the "persuasive intent" of advertising and resisting the techniques that marketers use to sell products

Module 2

- 1) What is “the first” ability that can help you to make good decisions?
 - a) Ability to ask the right question
 - b) Ability to search for information
 - c) Ability to analyse research results

- 2) Where is the “information need” located in the Maslow pyramid of needs?
 - a) At the base of the pyramid
 - b) At all levels

- c) At the top of the pyramid
- 3) Why is it important to ask the right question?
- a) Knowing what you are looking for will help you recognize when you have found the answer
 - b) Preparing an extensive report will help you to be more visible in society
 - c) You can prove that you are a good researcher
- 4) As you seek to resolve a situation, you will need to take a few steps. You have already searched and found enough information on a certain topic. What will you do next?
- a) Publish the results
 - b) Evaluate the authenticity of the information
 - c) Put them in a blog for others to comment on

Module 3

- 1) What does Intellectual Property (IP) refer to?
- a) Creations of the mind such as inventions, literary and artistic works, designs, symbols, names and images used in trade
 - b) Research studies published by academicians
 - c) Only patented inventions recognized by an international organization
- 2) Can you use copyrighted materials without a license?
- a) Yes, if they are available on the internet
 - b) Not at all
 - c) Yes, for a few purposes: commentary, research, teaching
- 3) What is the main reason for which media creators use implicit and explicit messages?
- a) To encourage people to read more carefully to deconstruct the messages
 - b) To influence and inform the audience
 - c) To make the messages more attractive
- 4) How can you improve your ability to understand media messages?
- a) Always looking for biased media messages
 - b) Becoming aware of the techniques used to create media messages
 - c) Ignoring implicit messages and focusing on the explicit messages

Module 4

- 1) What do we mean by “media messages are constructed”?
 - a) Media messages contain multiple items, text/audio messages and embedded values
 - b) The messages are assembled to transmit entirely accurate reflections of the real world
 - c) The messages are assembled containing only the beliefs of the media creator

- 2) What are the individual factors that usually affect the interpretation of media messages?
 - a) Religion, because individual beliefs may be very strong
 - b) Culture, because individuals can take away different meanings from the same product
 - c) Age, gender, race, religion, nationality, culture, social status of individuals

- 3) Media has social and political implications. How can media influence politics?
 - a) Social media platforms present all information for the development of a democratic process
 - b) Digital media provides sufficient news to avoid exchanging people opinions on political issues
 - c) Social media platforms can mobilize large-scale social and political protests around the world

- 4) How do subliminal messages act?
 - a) Using visual or auditory stimuli that the conscious mind cannot perceive, to strengthen the persuasiveness of advertisements
 - b) Using hidden words, ideas and imagery in print advertisements to help the auditorium immediately detect the subliminal message
 - c) Using different camera angles or lighting to make the consumers understand how reality is like

Module 5

- 1) Which of the following is an advantage of print media?
 - a) It is very easy and affordable to print and publish printed media
 - b) They are a widely trusted resource for relevant and fact-checked information
 - c) The news can be spread out to a massive global audience

- 2) Outdoor advertising has many advantages and a few disadvantages. Which of the following can count as a disadvantage of outdoor advertising?
 - a) There is a limited message transmitted
 - b) It is very expensive

- c) Addresses only pedestrians
- 3) Which of the following is a big disadvantage of using digital mass media?
- a) Digital mass media offer easy ways to spread news and information
 - b) Digital mass media can connect people around the world, but it can disconnect from the people in front of us
 - c) Digital mass media can mobilize masses of people for a specific topic
- 4) It is said that manipulative media is a very important tool in learning. Why?
- a) Manipulative media involves people in learning manipulative techniques
 - b) It provides students with tools for creating a manipulative environment
 - c) Manipulative media allows students to explore and investigate

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Appendix

Assessment quiz check sheets

Evaluation quiz Module 1 check sheet – correct answers

1b

2b

3a

4c

Evaluation quiz Module 2 check sheet – correct answers

1a

2b

3a

4b

Evaluation quiz Module 3 check sheet – correct answers

1a

2c

3b

4b

Evaluation quiz Module 4 check sheet – correct answers

1a

2c

3c

4a

Evaluation quiz Module 5 check sheet – correct answers

1b

2a

3b

4c

Instructional design review checklist for youth workers

No	Criteria	Yes	No
1. Objectives			
1.1	Are objectives stated clearly for the learner?		
1.2	Are the course requirements consistent with the objectives?		
1.3	Do chapters/topics thoroughly cover the course's objectives?		
1.4	Do the learning objectives match the learning outcomes?		
1.5	Does the overall content and structure of the course meet its instructional objectives?		
2. Structure			
2.1	Does the course have a concise and comprehensive overview or syllabus?		
2.2	Does the course include examples, analogies, case studies, simulations, graphical representations, and interactive questions?		
2.3	Does the course structure use appropriate methods and procedures to measure student mastery?		
3. Content			
3.1	Does the content flow seamlessly, without grammatical, syntactical and typing errors?		
3.2	Is the content up-to-date?		
3.3	Is the content aligned with the curriculum?		
3.4	Are the desirable outcomes incorporated in the content?		
3.5	Is the content in compliance with copyright laws and all its quoted material cited correctly?		
3.6	Does the course engage students in critical and abstract thinking?		
3.7	Does the course have prerequisites or require a technical background?		
4. Assessment			
4.1	Are the assignments relevant, efficient and engage students in a variety of performance types and activities?		
4.2	Are practice and assessment questions interactive?		
4.3	Do the practice and assessment tasks focus on the course's objectives?		
5. Technology - Design			
5.1	Is the design clear and consistent, with appropriate directions?		
5.2	Are the images and graphics of high quality and suitable for the course?		
5.3	Is the course easy to navigate and offers assistance with technical and course management?		
5.4	Is the course navigation structure consistent and reliable?		
5.5	Are the course hardware and software-defined?		
5.6	Is the audio and on-screen text in sync?		
5.7	Does the architecture of the course allow instructors to add content, activities and extra assessments?		

Feedback on topic for students

Assessment of Module						
Course title:						
Module Title:						
Part A:	On a scale of 1-5 where 1 is the lowest and 5 the highest level of agreement indicate how you feel on the following					
	Observations	1	2	3	4	5
1	The subject was interesting					
2	I believe the topics covered were important					
3	I would like to know more about the area					
4	I have learned new things which I am likely to apply in the future					
5	I would like to improve my skills in the area					
6	I am likely to recommend this course					
Part B:	In the space provided please feel free to include any comments and recommendations you wish to make					
Part C:	In the space provided please feel free to include your email address if you would like to be kept informed about this project					